

II. Workshop on vitamin C in immunology and cancer

Chairman: L. PAULING (USA)

Panel: R. ANDERSON (South Africa), S. BANIČ (Yugoslavia), T. K. BASU (England), G. KALLISTRATOS (Greece), A. MURATA (Japan), R. PANUSH (USA), D. SCHMÄHL (Germany), B. V. SIEGEL (USA)

The chairman welcomed the participants and the audience to this workshop and asked Prof. KALLISTRATOS to present his findings on the action of vitamin C in autochthon tumours.

KALLISTRATOS: I wish to report here about the elucidation of the antitumour activity of vitamin C in autochthon tumours induced by environmental carcinogens.

In order to find out if vitamin C has any protective effect against environmental carcinogenesis, it is necessary to determine the carcinogenic potency of the carcinogens present in the world in which we live. The carcinogenic activity of the carcinogen is proportional to the percentage of the tumours induced by the tumourigenic agent and reciprocal to the survival time in days. This means that a strong carcinogen is defined as a compound which induces a high percentage of tumours and, according to the degree of their malignancy, decreases markedly the survival time of the exposed organism.

Therefore it is obvious that substances which are able to reduce or prevent the tumour incidence caused by carcinogens and prolong the survival time of a tumour-bearing organism, are good anti-carcinogens.

The anti-carcinogenic properties of vitamin C were investigated in our laboratories in the Federal Republic of Germany and in Greece in benzo(a)pyrene-induced tumours. We chose benzo(a)pyrene for our studies because it is a strong environmental carcinogen which, under certain experimental conditions, induces a high percentage of malignant tumours. For example in mice and rats it induces about 100% tumours.

Furthermore, benzo(a)pyrene has a relatively simple chemical structure. It is composed of 5 aromatic rings containing 10 groups of double bonds with a high electron density in the so-called K region which is assumed to be responsible for its carcinogenic properties. The carcinogenic potency of benzo(a)pyrene was determined in mice and was found to be very high, with a value of about 65%.

Vitamin C was included in our investigations mainly for two reasons. First, because of the very promising reports of Prof. PAULING and his co-workers who stimulated us to examine more carefully the role of vitamin C in cancer prevention and treatment, and the second reason was that we found experimentally that some animals such as cows, pigs and others, are less susceptible to strong carcinogens such as benzo(a)pyrene. We would say, after the paper of Prof. SCHMÄHL, that they have a negative

disposition against benzo(a)pyrene carcinogenesis. We assumed that the less susceptible animals possess a biological inactivation mechanism, which, by means of natural anti-carcinogens, reduces the carcinogenic potency of benzo(a)pyrene, thus inhibiting the induction of tumours.

Further experimental studies demonstrated that the number of naturally occurring anti-carcinogens, most of them with known chemical structure, are present in varying concentrations in different animal species and could protect animals from carcinogenic exposure.

Among the naturally occurring anti-carcinogens I would like to mention the sulfhydryl derivatives, the unsaturated aliphatic acids and the basic compounds like mono-, di- and polyamines.

Ascorbic acid belongs to the group of unsaturated aliphatic acids which are known to reduce the carcinogenic potency of benzo(a)pyrene, for example, linoleic acid, cis-aconitic acid, as well as synthetically prepared maleic acid derivatives, acetylenedicarboxylic acid, etc.

These theoretical assumptions were also proved experimentally in mice and rats, and it was found that ascorbic acid reduces markedly the incidence of tumours caused by benzo(a)pyrene from 97% to 30%, and prolonged the survival time of the tumour-bearing animals. The carcinogenic potency of benzo(a)pyrene was diminished from 65% down to 21%. Further studies with different concentrations of vitamin C are continuing in our laboratories and indicate that the carcinogenic potency of benzo(a)pyrene could be further reduced by increasing the dosage of ascorbic acid. A very important observation is that benzo(a)pyrene-induced tumours, in spite of vitamin C administration, grew very slowly and are markedly smaller in comparison to benzo(a)pyrene-induced tumours without vitamin C – about one tenth of the size. Furthermore, histologically, there are fewer malignant cells than in the benzo(a)pyrene group. Cell division is inhibited and areas where tumour cells were killed were replaced by connective tissues.

For example, rhabdomyosarcoma of a rat treated with benzo(a)pyrene alone had a weight of about 150 g. The section preparation contained many malignant cells and lots of cell divisions, but in the other animals treated with benzo(a)pyrene plus ascorbic acid, there was only a slow growth of rhabdomyosarcoma weighing one tenth of that in the group which was treated only with benzo(a)pyrene. There was vast destruction of cancer cells and replacement with connective tissue. In conclusion, vitamin C possesses a marked anti-tumour activity against benzo(a)pyrene-induced autochthon tumours.

FERREIRA DA SILVA: I want to ask Prof. KALLISTRATOS which dose he uses to treat cancer. If I remember well, in the last Symposium 10 g a day were recommended.

KALLISTRATOS: We have not yet started any clinical trials, although we have here a protocol for a clinical trial. Our experimental results are mainly based on the action

of vitamin C in rats and mice. We administer vitamin C orally and we add some sugar for three reasons: First of all, because the animals drink better if they have a sweet solution, secondly, because sugar makes the animals very thirsty so that they drink a greater amount of vitamin C and, thirdly, tumour-bearing animals have a tumour cachexia and supplementary administration of some calories is useful. The calculated daily dosage was approximately 525 mg per rat and per day.

PAULING: Dr. CAMERON usually gives patients 10 g vitamin C per day for the rest of their lives, never stopping, never decreasing the amounts. He has gone as high as 45 g a day. In Dr. MURATA'S presentation of the work done in Japan, the dosages went up to 35 g per day, with most patients getting 8 or 10 g per day.

SIEGEL: Since this session is on immunology and cancer, maybe a background ought to be set for this topic. That is, just what is immunology as it relates to tumours and cancers?

All immunology begins with an antigen and, beginning with a tumour-associated antigen, I might say that I am not referring to this as a tumour antigen because we do not really know tumour antigens, but we do know about antigens that are associated with tumours. Tumour-associated antigens can react with any of the three main cell types in the circulation: macrophages, T-lymphocytes or B-lymphocytes, and what we think usually happens, is that the antigen is first processed by the macrophages and then interacts with the lymphocytes which are now sensitized, and are immunocytes because they are able to recognize an antigen. Two of the sensitized products of this interaction are the helper-cell and the suppressor-cell, although we will not be talking about suppressor-cells here. The helper-cell can provide the stimulus for the B-lymphocytes. I might just say that the T-lymphocyte is a lymphocyte that has been processed in the thymus. The B-cells have been processed in the bone marrow and can go on producing plasma cells and antibodies. Coming back to our sensitized lymphocytes, some of these lymphocytes are cytotoxic to tumour cells and so they will go on and destroy the tumour cell.

The T-lymphocytes, in interacting with the specific antigen, give rise to literally a multitude of soluble products or, as we refer to them, soluble mediators or lymphokines. One of these is the macrophage migration inhibition factor which, when acting on macrophages, traps them. If this happens in the vicinity of the cancer, the macrophages will be trapped in the cancer. Another lymphokine is the macrophage-activating factor which somehow activates the macrophage, stimulates the metabolic processes as it were, so that now the macrophage becomes activated and, in becoming activated is able to non-specifically attack tumour cells, thereby destroying them. So we have two ways in which tumour cells can be destroyed by the immune process. We have the cytotoxic T-cell which can destroy the tumour directly and then we have the macrophage which becomes activated by lymphokines and can go on to destroy the tumour cells.

Interferon is also one of the lymphokines. It does not have to be added from the outside but you can catalyze or aid the process just by adding interferon which is, of course, what we are trying to do now. Clinicians are testing interferon, very actively. As for the B-cells, they can, with the help of the helper-cells, interact with the processed antigens to differentiate, multiply and produce plasma cells that are responsible for the production of circulating antibodies.

Antibody can combine with complement and, in doing so, becomes highly destructive to tumour cells. Antibody can also simply coat the tumour and perhaps do nothing. However, when the antibody-coated tumour cells come into contact with so-called killer-cells which are present in the body – these are frequently referred to as null cells because they are neither T-cells nor B-cells –, they can be destroyed. Finally, there exist natural killer-cells about which little is known except that they are present at certain periods in our lives and are capable of destroying tumour cells. At this time, however, we are not too certain whether these cells are macrophages or lymphocytes.

Now you might ask: With this magnificent system, why is it that we are not able to counteract the tumour? Why is not our immune system, which is highly sophisticated, highly refined and highly effective, able to cope with tumours? One reason is that tumours are immuno-suppressive, that is, people who have tumourous growths also have defective immune reactions. They are not able to respond normally, or as readily, and so this is one reason why we are not able to cope with tumours from the immunological point of view. There are also other reasons: The tumour is described as “sneaking through”. In other words, it grows so fast that the immune system does not have time to react to it. This is another theory and is true in some cases.

There are other theories concerning our inability to cope with tumours, despite such a fine immune system. One is that the tumour sheds its antigens which then combine with the circulating lymphocytes, depriving them of their capacity to act as killer lymphocytes. They are “tied up” as it were.

Those are the main theories. There are satellite theories to these theories. I thought, Prof. PAULING, that this would provide some background. Now the question that we might ask is: “How can vitamin C intercede in this system?”

PAULING: Thank you, Prof. SIEGEL. Does any member want to comment?

SCHMÄHL: Please allow me to make some critical remarks about our topic “immune therapy of cancer and vitamin C”. I think to speak about this point is rather difficult for us because we know that cancer is not “Cancer”. We have to distinguish at least one hundred or more different types of the disease, each with its own etiology, its own prognosis, its own clinical entity and its own therapy. On the basis of present knowledge, it is improbable that any agent would attack all types of cancer in the same way. So, I would prefer to discuss specific types of cancer, such as colon cancer, stomach cancer or breast cancer.

My second critical point is that the hopes in the USA about the immune therapy of cancer have now dropped to zero point. Remember, too, the Cancer Act of President Nixon about 8 years ago? Immunology and cancer have accounted for about 70% of the medical research activities, with a lot of money, and all this has now been cut because the expectations have not been fulfilled and the immunotherapy of cancer today remains an unrealized dream. I want to ask you, have you ever seen one type of cancer where the cancer was destroyed in such a way? I have never seen this in my life and also I do not believe that each cancer patient during the development of the disease has an immune deficiency. This may be so in a last, latent stage of the disease, but not at the beginning.

The same is true for interferon. Up to now we have about 120 cases in the world that have been treated with interferon. About 90% of these cases did not respond. About 10% did respond for a very short time but the frequency of toxic side effects of this compound was rather high. So I think if we speak here in public, we should raise no great hopes. Maybe the situation will change in 10 years, but today we must say that the situation is not as glamorous as we might wish.

Now, my last point: vitamin C and cancer. I think vitamin C up to now is a drug with such a good reputation that we should be very careful not to turn it into, maybe, a bad reputation by raising hopes today which may not be fulfilled in the future. If we look critically, we have two studies, the study by Dr. CAMERON which is an uncontrolled clinical study and that of the Mayo Clinic which has produced negative results. What we have to do now, and in the future, if we believe that vitamin C may have a beneficial effect in cancer, is to create basic clinical and experimental studies. We then have to look at them very critically and maybe in two years or so we can determine whether vitamin C is also a beneficial drug in cancer. At the moment I would recommend reserve.

PAULING: Thank you, Prof. SCHMÄHL. I will make a comment about each of these points.

First of all, in my opinion there is much evidence that at least strongly indicates that the body's natural protective mechanisms can be, and often are effective against cancer. It is found especially in Germany where autopsies are carried out that essentially every man has cancer of the prostate and yet in only a small fraction of them has this cancer of the prostate developed to such an extent as to kill him. So we can ask: What is it that keeps the cancer under control? It is observed that after the surgical removal of a malignant tumour there are millions of malignant cells in the circulation of essentially every patient and yet many of these patients never develop metastases. So we can ask: What happens to these circulating malignant cells? Of course, with the majority of the patients, metastases do develop so that whatever the protective mechanism is, it is not 100% effective. I believe that there is much evidence that the body's natural protective mechanisms, presumably the immune mechanism to a large part, are often effective. This is promising because, if they are effective in a certain percentage of the cases, 20% say; that means that enhancing their effectiveness

will save a large number of persons from developing and dying of cancer. So I think that there is really sound reason to believe that immune surveillance does operate and is often effective in controlling cancer.

Now, as to the clinical work on cancer and vitamin C, Prof. SCHMÄHL said that Dr. CAMERON'S studies were uncontrolled. This is not true because this study had retrospective controls, 300 of which were contemporaneous with the ascorbate-treated patients and in the same hospital. It was not a double-blind prospective trial, but it was also not an uncontrolled study. Prof. SCHMÄHL also mentioned the work of the Mayo Clinic and said that this gave negative results. This too is not true. It gave positive results in that the treated patients got along better than the controls. There were two statistically significant differences. Twice as many of the treated patients had less pain than the controls. This was a statistically significant result, and they had greater energy than the controls and this was a statistically significant result. They also lived longer, but not by the very large difference that was observed by Dr. CAMERON and the difference in survival time was not a statistically significant result. So it is wrong to say that the Mayo Clinic gave negative results. It gave positive results, although not so great as those Dr. CAMERON has reported. On the other hand, in the third retrospective, controlled trial which Dr. MURATA reported on, essentially the same results were obtained as in CAMERON'S observations. Vitamin C should be used as a supplement to conventional therapy of all kinds even if chemotherapy seems to be worthwhile, and I think that it should be used along with the chemotherapy. Of course, the results obtained with chemotherapy for most kinds of cancer are not nearly so good as those reported by Dr. CAMERON for treatment with vitamin C alone. Here we have an unusual substance which is not like a new anti-cancer drug. We do not require a careful trial of toxicity to allay fears about long-term serious side effects. It is a non-toxic substance with which human beings and their predecessors have had millions of years of experience. A negative attitude is therefore really not justified.

Does anyone else wish to comment?

BASU: During the last decade we have had biochemical evidence, clinical evidence, and experimental evidence suggesting that vitamin C may be beneficial in malignant diseases. But the clinical evidence – I am repeating with due respect to Prof. PAULING – is based on non-randomized trials. We were also over-enthusiastic about the results we have obtained. We have given large doses, but in isolated cases. We have found that they induce a tremendous response. What we desperately need, however, are randomized properly controlled trials in different centres, i. e. two multi-centre programmes that will eliminate bias. Once we establish that indeed vitamin C can have a beneficial effect on the disease, then we have got to establish the dose because, as Prof. PAULING mentioned, if vitamin C should be used as a conventional therapy, we have got to determine the therapeutic dose, as all conventional drugs have a specific dose. Otherwise in one centre, one might be using 35 g or 100 g, another centre 5 g. Therefore we are not able to establish the facts and we are not able to convince the

clinicians on a worldwide basis to give supplements of vitamin C in large doses to treat malignant diseases. So we need to do randomized trials in various centres. We are contemplating starting in England, but this will take some time.

HORNIG: We have controversial data, as we have just heard. We have the data of the Mayo Clinic. We have Prof. PAULING'S data. We have the data of Dr. MURATA. I think the primary task is to identify where are the most important gaps. What can be done in the sense that vitamin C is, on the one hand, useful in cancer therapy and in immunocompetence, and what can be done, on the other hand, to demonstrate that vitamin C is as safe a compound as Prof. SCHMÄHL indicated. It has not been shown that vitamin C given in such tremendous amounts as have been mentioned today, is absorbed at all, and how are these high doses of vitamin C metabolized?

PAULING: Dr. Fred KLENNER, I think 15 years ago, reported that he had given 125 g of sodium ascorbate by intravenous infusion in a period of 10 hours to a young woman in a coma. She immediately came out of the coma and was in good shape the next day. There are reports of this sort about the tolerance of the body to large amounts of sodium ascorbate. But of course I think additional studies should be made.

WILSON: Mr. Chairman, I think that some points have been made about the use of vitamin C in the treatment of cancer. I think that perhaps we could make a parallel between the use of vitamin C for the treatment of cancer and the use of, shall we say, Epanutin for the treatment of epilepsy or of digoxin for the treatment of cardiac failure. One of the basic points of the two latter drugs is that we have to establish the drug levels of the patients when they are being treated. To what extent has this been done in the treatment of cancer? I am not sure, but certainly from our experience I know that, when a person has cancer, the ascorbic acid levels in the tissues are significantly and very drastically reduced. Let us compare this with, for example, insulin in the treatment of diabetes: If you do not give enough insulin, the blood sugar increases and more insulin is required. In cancer, the levels of vitamin C are reduced. Logically, therefore, we should give enough vitamin C to restore the normal levels. It seems obvious that, whether or not vitamin C is effective in cancer, one of the things that should be done in such patients is to try to establish a normal blood level of ascorbic acid and, at the same time, a normal tissue level. I would like to suggest this as one of the first things that we should look at in cancer patients. What happens with the vitamin C which we administer? Epidemiological studies, which have been suggested, are difficult with a condition like cancer where the person normally has vitamin C in his blood. It is extremely difficult to know what is happening to that ascorbic acid with reference to the ascorbic acid which is administered. Therefore, epidemiological studies, in my opinion, are relatively useless, except when they are done in the way Dr. MURATA did them on an all-or-none basis. Unless we control the blood levels we do not know what we are doing. This seems to be the only way of

doing a trial of this nature on an epidemiological basis. One can, as Prof. SCHMÄHL suggested, select certain types of cancer, but, even in the early days of penicillin, FLEMING was not terribly precise about the type of germ he initially treated. He found that penicillin was effective against a large number of gram-positive organisms. So I do not think on that ground that we can say one should only use vitamin C on a specific kind of cancer. We have historical precedents to show that that procedure is incorrect when we are investigating a new compound.

PAULING: Thank you. I would like to comment. Dr. CAMERON began treating patients with cancer by giving them large doses of ascorbic acid 9 years ago. Very quickly he got some money from the Scottish Health Board, and began making determinations of the serum, the plasma ascorbate and the leucocyte ascorbate. He has recorded these values for hundreds of patients. They are the basis of a page of comment in our book, but the material has not yet been published in detail. This work is being continued yet, obviously, much more needs to be done.

Also, if one looks at the material's balance of ascorbate, one finds that much of it disappears in the body in a way that is not well understood, although it is known to form oxidation products. Therefore, in our laboratory, for the last 3 years we have been developing micromethods of analysing for these various oxidation products, to determine what happens to them and their concentrations in different organs. I think that we should be studying the physiological properties of these oxidation products to see to what extent they, rather than ascorbate and dehydroascorbate, are responsible for the beneficial effects of ascorbic acid. A tremendous amount of work needs to be done and I am sure members of the panel could suggest other projects.

KALLISTRATOS: With respect to tolerance I would like to comment, we administer a daily dosage of 500 mg ascorbic acid which is calculated to be about 2.5g/kg and corresponds to a total daily dosage of about 150 g for a human being weighing 60 kg. This dosage is administered for 6 months and we have not observed any pathological alteration of the organs when killing the animals after 6 months.

BASU: That is fair enough as long as they are experimental animals, for which one can control the environmental and dietary factors. However, the situation in the human is different altogether. One does not know the nutritional status, for example, the sulphur-amino acid status, because we have shown that vitamin C in large doses deranges the metabolism of cysteine in order to be metabolized as ascorbate to sulphate. So, if sulphate levels are marginal, then one might perhaps become deficient in sulphate if one takes too much vitamin C. Furthermore, if such a subject is exposed to cyanide-containing substances or smokes, then there will be impairment in the detoxication of cyanide to thiocyanate because this process requires cysteine. If the subject is taking drugs such as salicylamide or acetaminophenacn which are also metabolized through sulphate conjugation, then there will be competition between vitamin C and the drug for sulphate. The person may experience a deleterious effect

from that large dosage of vitamin C. Then again, there is individual variation and so one has to be careful before extrapolating experimental results to a human situation. We are really talking at two different levels.

HORNIG: I just want to say that one should not take data from animals in which the metabolism of ascorbic acid is completely different to that of humans, especially from the rat, because the absorption of ascorbic acid in rats is different from that in man or in the guinea-pig. This should be taken into account.

SIEGEL: In connection with studies on oxidation products we have looked, not very extensively, at this point, at the ratios of oxidation/reduction of ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid in the tissues particularly in spleens which are the main producers of antibody in aging animals and those developing cancer. We find that the oxidation reduction ratio increases quite significantly. In other words, the ascorbic acid component of the vitamin C diminishes with age and, seemingly, with the development of cancer. So here we have a suggestion that, if one adds the reduced product, that is the ascorbic acid, one might have an ameliorative effect.

Now an answer to how some people on the panel might feel as to "Where do we go from here?" Whether we have to feel as discouraged about interferon as Prof. SCHMÄHL was implying because he was talking about interferon that is produced outside the body and then administered exogenously?

The interferon I am talking about is produced by the host and is of a different kind. It is also very important to remember that interferon is very expensive and scarce. It will take years before it has developed to a stage where it can be studied on a wider scale.

BANIČ: As one member of the panel, I would like to say that vitamin C can be of great benefit through its enhancement of interferon synthesis and its activation of T-cells which play a very important role in the destruction of tumour cells, both in animals and man. I have nothing to say about vitamin C and cancer because I have no personal experience, although I am starting some experimental work on guinea-pigs with tumours. Up to now, I have no results, but I would like to stress some other points. It appears to me that the most beneficial effect of vitamin C can be observed in those people who have low vitamin C levels in their tissues and plasma. For that reason I am of the opinion that it would be a wonderful practice if, in all hospitals, or at least in almost all patients, the vitamin C status could be determined in the biochemical laboratories. On the basis of the results of such determinations one could select those patients requiring supplementary vitamin C in addition to their other treatment. I believe that there are many such patients with various diseases, not only infectious diseases, but also conditions requiring surgery. It is quite clear today that many people in all countries have low tissue vitamin concentrations. We heard two years ago about the data of Dr. SCHORAH in England who demonstrated beautifully that many people there have a very low vitamin C status. It is also known that the

intake of vitamin C in food was only about 20 mg during the Second World War in England. This was still satisfactory in preventing scurvy but was no longer optimal.

In conclusion, I would like to say that the individual requirements of vitamin C are different in different people: for the majority of people, relatively low doses are sufficient, but there are individuals who require 5 or 10 times more vitamin C. This point was stressed by Prof. WILSON.

In the literature there are also data from guinea-pigs, demonstrating that, in these animals, too, there is substantial interindividual variation in vitamin C requirement: some need lower amounts, whereas others need 5 or 10 times as much.

ANDERSON: To comment on Prof. SIEGEL'S findings: I think our papers at this symposium have, in fact, been complementary. We have also found that vitamin C possesses immunostimulatory activity which seems to be completely related to its ability to scavenge oxidative-free radicals. These agents have an inhibitory effect on immune responsiveness. As I pointed out yesterday, the functions of both phagocytic cells and T-lymphocytes are considerably enhanced in the presence of ascorbic acid. Therefore, we would consider ascorbic acid to be a non-specific immunostimulant, in which respect it is not unique. Another agent which possesses these properties is levamisol which has a profile of effects on immune responses similar to that of ascorbic acid, the difference, of course, being that ascorbic acid has minimal side effects and can be used in very high doses. We, in fact, have no experience in the use of ascorbic acid in cancer, but if it is a non-specific immunostimulant as we would suggest, one would imagine that it would be useful in the therapy of all types of cancer.

PAULING: Since time is running out, perhaps I may be allowed to make some final remarks.

Dr. CAMERON, in his talk that he prepared for delivery here and that I read in part yesterday, made the statement that part of the reason for the enthusiasm of lay people for treatment with ascorbic acid is their disillusionment with the conventional therapies and their lack of confidence. Well, he did not need to say "laymen". He could have included the physicians themselves. We get hundreds of letters and phone calls from people with cancer and I have calculated that a physician who develops cancer is one hundred times more likely to write to us or telephone us to get information about vitamin C than a lay person who develops cancer. The physicians themselves are interested if they get cancer, or if a member of their family gets cancer. I would ask: Supposing that you developed cancer of the colon? Chemotherapy and radiation have essentially no value, and if it is inoperable cancer or the operation has been carried out, what are you going to do? Perhaps you can take laetril or some other unconventional treatment of that sort. But there is one thing that can give you some hope and that is to take large amounts of vitamin C. The one message that I want to give to physicians is this:

I have received scores, in fact hundreds, of letters from people with cancer who have asked a physician whether they could be given vitamin C. The physician has replied that this is nonsense, quackery, or has made some stronger statement. This, of course, does not have a good impression on the patient. In recent months, however, it has seemed to me that physicians are becoming increasingly tolerant about vitamin C and, instead of just rejecting it, or saying, "If you need vitamin C, you have to go to some other doctor", they are saying, "Well, it will not do any good, but if you want to take it, all right, go ahead and take it." My message to physicians is: "If a patient with cancer wants to be given, or wants to take large doses of vitamin C, do not reject the idea. There is no side effect, no long-term effect from vitamin C that is comparable in severity with the dying of cancer in a few months or a year or two that these patients otherwise face."

I thank the members of the panel and the members of the audience for their contributions.

International Journal for Vitamin and Nutrition Research
Internationale Zeitschrift für Vitamin- und Ernährungsforschung
Journal international de Vitaminologie et de Nutrition
Supplement No. 23

VITAMIN C

NEW CLINICAL APPLICATIONS
IN IMMUNOLOGY, LIPID METABOLISM
AND CANCER

Edited by A. Hanck

Hans Huber Publishers Bern Stuttgart Vienna

CIP-Kurztitelaufnahme der Deutschen Bibliothek

Hanck, A.

VITAMIN C

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Bern, Stuttgart, Wien: Huber, 1982

ISBN 3-456-81200-0

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Foreword

International Symposia on vitamin C in Brazil have almost become a tradition. After the extremely successful Symposia held in Rio de Janeiro in 1976 and 1978, a Third International Symposium on vitamin C was held in São Paulo from the 8th to the 10th September 1980 under the auspices of the Academia Brasileira de Medicina Militar and the Medical Faculty of the State University of São Paulo. The Symposium was chaired by Linus Pauling, Bras Itapaci Magalhães and Alfred Hanck.

Central topics were new findings on the role of vitamin C in immunology, in cancer and in lipid metabolism. Workshops produced fruitful discussions of new findings and current aspects, aiming at a better understanding of the role of vitamin C in health and disease. These may help in decision-making for further research and practical application of our present knowledge.

It is hoped that this book will reach as broad an audience as did these on previous Symposia, adding to the medical knowledge about vitamin C, not least for the benefit of the patients.

A. Hanck